

Oplismenus frumentaceus (Jhangora) husk for activated carbon preparation and its use in adsorption of Brilliant Green dye from aqueous solution

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Abstract : In the present study, activated carbon had been prepared from *Oplismenus frumentaceus* (Jhangora) husk for the removal of Brilliant Green dye (BG) from aqueous solution. The surface study of *Oplismenus frumentaceus* husk activated carbon (OFHC) was investigated using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Batch studies were performed to optimize various experimental parameters. Optimum conditions were found to be at initial pH = 7, contact time = 90 min and adsorbent dose = 4 g/L. The study also reveals that pH changes the structural stability of BG and its color intensity decreased as the pH increased. The equilibrium isotherm data were analyzed using Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm model. It was found that Freundlich equilibrium isotherm best fits in the experimental data. The results clearly showed that the multi layer adsorption capacity of OFHC was 20.83 mg/g. The adsorption of BG onto OFHC followed pseudo-second order kinetics. Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were also evaluated and the study reveals that adsorption of BG onto OFHC is favorably influenced by an increase in the temperature of the adsorption process. The experimental studies have indicated that OFHC could be employed as good alternative in wastewater treatment for the removal of BG.

Keywords : Brilliant Green dye, *Oplismenus frumentaceus*, adsorption isotherms, kinetics, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Dyes are widely used in many industries such as textile, fiber, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, leather, paper, plastic and printing. About 10000 different dyes are annually used to various industrial processes. Many of these have been identified as toxic or even carcinogenic¹. A large amount of dyes are discharged to the wastewater effluent annually that severely pollute the water body and damage the aquatic life by increasing the COD, BOD and suspended solid of the water body. Color interferes with penetration of sun light into water, retards photosynthesis, inhibits the growth of aquatic biota and interferes with the gas solubility of water bodies².

Brilliant Green is a basic organic dye belongs to the triphenylmethane family (Fig. 1) that is widely used in coloring the leather and fiber³. The dye causes eye burns, which may be responsible for permanent injury to the

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Brilliant Green.

eyes of human and, if swallowed it causes irritation to gastrointestinal track with symptoms of nausea, vomiting and diarrhea. It may also be harmful if inhaled. It is likely to cause irritation to the skin and respiratory track⁴. Thus it becomes necessary to remove Brilliant Green from waste water before it release into aquatic environment.

There are many chemical and physical methods such as flocculation, electrofloatation, precipitation, coagulation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, electro chemical destruction, irradiation, ozonation, and katox treatment method that have been used to treat the waste water having dyes⁵ but these processes are costly and can't be used effectively to treat a large quantity of dyes. However, adsorption is most suitable method for solving this type of problem. Several agro-industrial wastes/byproducts have been used for the adsorption of dyes.

These include hard wood⁶, banana pith⁷, Indian rose wood⁸, waste coir pith⁹, bagasse pith¹⁰, neem leaf powder⁴, banana and orange pith¹¹, barley husk¹², cassava peels¹³, rice husk and mahogany sawdust¹⁴ etc.

Generally adsorption capacity of crude agricultural byproduct is low. Chemical modifications can greatly improve the adsorption capacity of these biomaterials¹⁵. Nowadays activated carbon is widely used as adsorbent because of its large surface area, micro porous structure and high adsorption capacity etc.¹⁶. Many biomass have been investigated from the past for the preparation of activated carbon which include, wheat bran¹⁷, rice husk based activated carbon¹⁸, rice husk ash^{19,20}, formaldehyde treated, sulfuric acid treated sawdust and sodium hydroxide treated saw dust^{8,21,22}, de-oiled soya cake²³, bagasse fly ash²⁴, sugarcane dust²⁵, modified peat²⁶, sunflower cake²⁷, coconut fiber²⁸, *Borassus aethiopum* flower²⁹, jute sticks³⁰ and pine cone³¹ etc. But easily available, economical and highly effective adsorbent are still needed. *Oplismenus frumentaceus* (Common name : Jhangora) is a commonly grown cereal in the hilly area of Uttarakhand, India. The seed of this plant used for eating purpose as an alternative of rice. Its husk is a byproduct/waste that is used as fodder in a small amount and its large amount used to be burnt and it tends to cause air pollution.

The present work deals with the removal of BG from aqueous solution using activated carbon derived from *Oplismenus frumentaceus* husk (OFHC).

Results and discussion

Characterization of OFHC :

OFHC was characterized with respect to its surface functional groups using FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra (Fig. 2) showed that the OFHC has the functional

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of OFHC.

group $\text{CH}_2\text{-O-Si}$ which revealed from the appearance of peak in the region $900\text{--}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, peaks at $2962\text{--}2853\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to C-H stretching band and in $1385\text{--}1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to C-H bending, C-C multiple bond stretching occurs in the region $1680\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Amine group having N-H group ($\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$), N-H bending ($1600\text{--}1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and C-H vibration ($1340\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the peaks in the region $1070\text{--}1030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to stretching of S=O, the peak at in $\sim 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to $\text{CH}_2\text{-S-CH}_2$. The spectra also show presence of diketone stretching vibration in the region ($1640\text{--}1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$). EDAX study (Table 1) also supports the above FTIR prediction.

The scanning electron microscopic studies showed the availability of pores. It also revealed that OFHC particle is of irregular shape with rough surface, having heterogeneous pores (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. SEM photograph of OFHC.

Effect of initial dye concentration and contact time :

The effect of initial dye concentration and contact time on the removal of BG by OFHC is shown in Fig. 4. To evaluate the effect of initial dye concentration and contact time, the concentration varied from 10–50 mg/L, for adsorbent dose = 4 g/L at pH 7. The curve showed rapid adsorption of dye in the first 20 min even it is optimum time for the removal of lowest concentration (10 mg/L)

Fig. 4. Effect of initial dye concentration on adsorption of BG on OFHC.

of dye. The percent removal for the concentration 10 mg/L is 98.2%. It is so because active sites of adsorbent are sufficient. Where the optimum time for the highest dye concentration (50 mg/L) is 60 min and the maximum removal was 96.2%. Since there was no significant difference between the percentage removal of the dye concentration 10 mg/L and 50 mg/L, so, further experiments were carried out at the dye concentration 50 mg/L and 90 min was taken as optimum time.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on adsorption of BG onto OFHC shown in Fig. 5 where, initial dye concentration = 50 mg/L and adsorbent dose = 4 g/L. It was found that at low pH or at acidic medium the percent removal was low and as we increase the pH percentage removal of BG increases. Maximum removal was found around the range 10 then it becomes almost constant. This may be due to the fact that at low pH the number of negatively charged sites of adsorbent decreases as the H⁺ ion competes with the basic dye BG. The pH of the solution also affects the

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on BG adsorption on OFHC.

surface charge of the dye, therefore affect the structural stability of BG and hence, its color intensity. It was found that as the solution pH increased a color reduction of BG also increased. So, at the pH 3, which is natural pH of BG, removal was 87%. As we increase the pH its color intensity itself decreased and on adding adsorbent percentage removal enhanced. So, at the pH 7 percentage removal is 96 and almost 99% removal showed at pH 12.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

To study the effect of adsorbent dose, initial dye concentration was taken as 50 mg/L and pH was maintain at 7 and agitation time 90 min at 100 rpm. Adsorbent dose gives an idea about the effectiveness of the adsorbent. It was found that with the increase in adsorbent dose from 2 g/L to 10 g/L by a interval of 2 g/L, the percentage removal also increase up to a certain limit from 95.8–97.3% (Fig. 6) and then it remains constant. Since the percent removal is not significantly increased, this is due to sufficient active site for the 50 mg/L dye concentration at pH 7 (the color intensity itself reduced due to pH). The enhancement in the percentage of dye removal with increasing adsorbent dose is due to increase of sorption active sites at the adsorbent surface with increasing the dose.

Adsorption equilibrium isotherm :

The results of experimental were analyzed using Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models, as it is important to find best fit isotherm to evaluate the efficiency of prepared adsorbent to develop suitable industrial adsorption system designs.

Fig. 6. Effect of adsorbent dose on BG removal.

Langmuir isotherm :

The Langmuir isotherms are based on an assumption of monolayer adsorption on to a surface containing a finite number of adsorption sites of uniform energies of adsorption. It is represented as follows¹⁹ :

$$q_e = q_m K_L C_e / (1 + K_L C_e) \quad (1)$$

Linear form of this expression is

$$C_e/q_e = 1/q_m K_L + C_e/q_m \quad (2)$$

where, q_e (mg/g) and C_e (mg/L) are the amount of adsorbed adsorbate per unit weight of adsorbent and adsorbed adsorbate concentration in solution in equilibrium, respectively. The constant K_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and the K_L/q_m gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity, q_m . Therefore a plot of C_e/q_e versus C_e gives a straight line of slope $1/q_m$ and intercepts $1/q_m K_L$.

The essential factor of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in term of a dimensionless constant called separation factor (R_L , also called equilibrium parameter) which is defined by the following equation :

$$R_L = 1 / (1 + K_L C_0) \quad (3)$$

where C_0 (mg/L) is the initial adsorbate concentration and q_m (mg/g) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption. The value of R_L indicates the shape of the isotherm to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$). Linear ($R_L = 1$). Favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$) (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Langmuir isotherm (adsorbent dose = 4 g/L; pH = 7; T = 303 K; t = 90 min; agitation rate = 100 rpm).

Freundlich isotherm :

The Freundlich isotherm can be applied to non ideal adsorption on heterogeneous surface as well as multi-layer sorption and is expressed by the following equation⁵ :

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n} \quad (4)$$

A linear form of this expression is

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + 1/n \cdot \log C_e \quad (5)$$

where K_F ($\text{mg}^{1-1/n} \text{L}^{1/n} \text{g}^{-1}$) is the Freundlich constant and n is the Freundlich exponent. Therefore a plot of $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ enables the constant and exponent n to be determined.

Temkin isotherm :

The Temkin isotherm describes the behavior of adsorption systems on heterogeneous surface, and it has generally been applied in the following form⁵ :

$$q_e = RT/b \ln (AC_e) \quad (6)$$

A linear form of the Temkin isotherm can be expressed as

$$q_e = RT/b \ln A + RT/b \ln C_e \quad (7)$$

where, $RT/b = B$ the adsorption data can be analyzed according to eq. (7). Therefore, a plot of q_e versus $\ln C_e$ enables to determine the constants A and B .

The adsorption equilibrium isotherm is important for the description of how the adsorbate will interact with the adsorbent and give the idea about the adsorption capacity

of the adsorbent. To optimize the design of an adsorption system to remove BG from effluent system, it is important to establish the most appropriate correlation for the equilibrium curve. Hence, the correlation of equilibrium data using a theoretical equation is essential for the adsorption prediction of the extent of adsorption. Therefore, the equilibrium experimental data for adsorbed BG data on OFHC were analyzed using Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm equations. The adsorption isotherm plots are given in Figs. 7-9 and results are summarized

Fig. 8. Freundlich isotherm (adsorbent dose = 4 g/L; pH = 7; T = 303 K; t = 90 min; agitation rate = 100 rpm).

Fig. 9. Temkin isotherm (adsorbent dose = 4 g/L; pH = 7; T = 303 K; t = 90 min; agitation rate = 100 rpm).

in Table 2. By comparing correlation coefficient values obtained from the Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin equilibrium isotherm equation, it can be concluded that the

Table 1. EDAX study of OFHC

Element	Wt%	At%
C	73.83	79.77
O	23.08	18.72
Na	1.40	0.79
Si	0.57	0.26
S	1.12	0.45

data best fits in Freundlich isotherm model ($r^2 = 0.982$) as the Freundlich constant K_F , was 9.95 (between 1-10) and Freundlich exponent, n , is calculated 1.477 which is larger than 1 and indicate the favorable nature of adsorption.

The Temkin constant and the correlation coefficient value ($r^2 = 0.963$) are given in Table 2 and it was higher than Langmuir correlation coefficient value ($r^2 = 0.954$). Since the correlation coefficient in case of Langmuir isotherm is less than that of Freundlich and Temkin isotherm but the value of R_L fell in the range of 0-1 which shows that the adsorption process is also favorable and the mono layer adsorption capacity of BG onto OFHC is 20.83 mg/g.

So, from the above discussion it can be concluded that the Freundlich isotherm provides the best correlation for the experimental data, this suggests that adsorbate and adsorbent has a multi layer interaction and is derived by assuming heterogeneous surface with interaction between adsorbed molecules with a nonuniform distribution of heat of sorption over the surface of the adsorbent. Whereas the Temkin isotherm also supports adsorbate-adsorbate interactions. So, OFHC have both homogeneous and heterogeneous active sites. Table 3 shows the comparative adsorption capacity of BG onto various other adsorbents which were chemically treated.

Adsorption kinetics :

In order to investigate the mechanism of adsorption and to determine the rate controlling step the following kinetic rate equations have been used to test the experimental data.

Pseudo-first order equation :

The pseudo-first order equation of Lagergren is generally expressed as follows⁵ :

$$dq_t/dt = k_1(q_e - q_t) \tag{8}$$

After integrating and applying boundary condition, $t = 0$

Table 2. Analysis of Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin adsorption isotherm parameters for the adsorption of BG on OFHC

Langmuir			Freundlich				Temkin		
q_m (mg/g)	K_L	r^2	R_L	K_F (L/g)	n	r^2	B_1	K_T (L/g)	r^2
20.83	0.7	0.954	0.066–0.125	9.95	1.477	0.982	0.103	1.056	0.963

Table 3 Comparison of adsorption capacities of BG onto various adsorbents

Adsorbent	q_m (mg/g)	Ref.
Coal	0.929	32
Activated carbon prepared from acorn	2.11	33
Rice husk ash	26.18	19
NaOH treated saw dust	58.47	22
Coconut fiber activated carbon	9.09	27
OFHC	20.83	Present study

to $t = t$ and $q_t = 0$ to $q_t = q_t$; then integration from of eq. (8) becomes

$$q_t = q_e (1 - e^{-k_1 t}) \quad (9)$$

However, eq. (9) is transformed into its linear form for use in kinetic analysis of data as

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (10)$$

where, q_e (mg/L) and q_t (mg/g) are the amount of adsorbed adsorbate at equilibrium and at time t , respectively, and k_1 (min^{-1}) is the rate constant of pseudo-first order adsorption.

Pseudo-second order equation :

If the rate of adsorption has second-order mechanism, the pseudo-second order chemisorptions kinetic rate equation is expressed as follows⁵ :

$$dq_t/dt = k_2(q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (11)$$

Integrating this equation for the boundary condition, gives

$$1/(q_e - q_t) = 1/q_e + k_2 t \quad (12)$$

This is integrated rate law for pseudo-second order reaction. Eq. (12) can be rearranged to its linear form as

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e \cdot t \quad (13)$$

where, k_2 (g/mg min) is the equilibrium rate constant of pseudo-second order adsorption. If the pseudo-second order is applicable, the plot of t/q_e against t should given a linear relationship, from which q_e and k_2 can be determined from the slope and intercept of the plot, and there is no need to know any parameter beforehand.

To determine the kinetic mechanism that controls the

adsorption process, the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order were applied. As per Langergren pseudo-first order model, have a poor regression coefficient (R^2) in the range of 0.875–0.999 at different physicochemical condition hence not presented here. More over the calculated value of q_e with the experimental value of q_e , values for first-order differed a lot (Table 4), it indicate the inapplicability of this model. So, the adsorption data were then analyzed using pseudo-second order model Fig. 10 and the results of the kinetic parameter are showed in Table 4. The values of correlation coefficient (r^2) of pseudo-second order reactions are closer to unity in the range 0.999–0.998 and higher than that of pseudo-first order reaction. Whereas, the value of calculated equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) are closer to the experimental values of q_e . Also from Table 4, the values of rate constant, k_2 decreases with increasing initial dye concentration. The reason for this behavior may be due to the

Table 4. Adsorption kinetic parameter of Brilliant Green dye on OFHC

Kinetic model	10 mg/L	20 mg/L	30 mg/L	40 mg/L	50 mg/L
Pseudo-first order :					
k_1 (L/min)	12.34	25	43.47	50	45.45
$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	2.45	4.88	7.33	9.67	12.03
$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	2.68	1.24	1.35	1.33	2.65
r^2	0.999	0.921	0.875	0.957	0.989
Pseudo-second order :					
k_2 (g/mg min)	0.6617	0.2183	0.2496	0.1238	0.0383
$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	2.45	4.88	7.33	9.67	12.03
$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	2.49	4.97	7.4	9.8	12.35
r^2	0.998	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.998

lower competition for the sorption site at lower concentration. At higher concentration the competition for the active surface sites will be high so the lower sorption rates are obtained. Hence it can be concluded that the adsorption kinetics of BG is describe pseudo-second order chemical reaction.

Thermodynamic study :

The Gibbs free energy change of the adsorption pro-

cess is related to the equilibrium constant by the classic Van't Hoff equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (14)$$

where, ΔG° is free energy change (kJ mol^{-1}), T is the absolute temperature (K), R is universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol K}^{-1}$) and K is the Langmuir constant. According to thermodynamics, the Gibbs free energy change is also related to the entropy change and heat of adsorption at constant temperature by the following equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (15)$$

Combining above two equations, we get

$$\ln K = -\Delta G^\circ/RT = \Delta S^\circ/R - \Delta H^\circ/RT \quad (16)$$

where ΔH° the change in enthalpy (kJ mol^{-1}) and ΔS° the entropy change ($\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Thus ΔH° can be determined by the slope of the linear Van't Hoff plot, i.e. as $\ln K$ versus $(1/T)^{19}$ (Fig. 12).

The thermodynamic parameter for the adsorption of BG is given in Table 5. Negative value of ΔG° shows that adsorption process is spontaneous. Change in enthalpy ΔH° is positive indicating that the process is endothermic and the positive value of ΔS° shows increased disorder at the solid solution interphase during the adsorption of BG.

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameter for the adsorption of BG on OFHC

ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)			
		293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K
2.07	13.30	-3.89	-4.03	-4.16	-4.29

Conclusion :

The present study shows that *Oplismenus frumentaceus* husk derived activated carbon; an agricultural byproduct can be used as low cost effective alternative adsorbent for the removal of Brilliant Green dye from wastewater. The adsorption capacity for Brilliant Green dye of activated carbon thus derived is higher in comparison to many other adsorbents (~21 mg/g). It is found that percentage removal increases as we increase the contact time, pH and amount of adsorbent dose. But percentage removal decreases as we increase the initial BG concentration. Kinetic experiments clearly indicate that Brilliant Green dye adsorption follows pseudo-second order kinetic model and adsorption was controlled by chemisorptions process.

Fig. 10. Pseudo-second order model (adsorbent dose = 4 g/25 L; pH = 7; 303 = K; t = 90 min; agitation rate 100 rpm).

Fig. 11. Plot of $\ln K$ versus $1/T$ for the estimation of thermodynamic parameter (adsorbent dose = 4 g/L; pH = 7; T = 303 K; t = 90 min; agitation rate 100 rpm).

Freundlich isotherm model gave best fitting with experimental data then Langmuir and Temkin model. Adsorption of BG on OFHC is favorably influence by an increased in the temperature so the process is endothermic and the negative value of ΔG° indicates spontaneous adsorption of BG on OFHC.

Materials and methods :

Absorbent :

Oplismenus frumentaceus husk were obtained from a local mill of Pauri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India. The husk

was washed with distilled water to remove adhering dirt and soluble impurities and dried at 80 °C for 24 h. The dried husk was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (98% pure) in 1 : 1 ratio since the acid was so strong so the dried husk burnt and carbon was formed keep it for 48 h. The carbonized biomass is then washed with several times with distilled water and soaked in 1% sodium bicarbonate solution over night to remove residual acid so it become neutral. The neutralized carbon was dried in hot air oven at 150 °C for 48 h for activation. The dried husk activated carbon was then sieved to 25 mm mesh size and used as adsorbent.

Dye solution and other chemical :

Brilliant Green dye having molecular formula $C_{27}H_{34}O_4N_2S$, C.I. No. = 42040, nature = basic dye, m.p. = 210 °C, λ_{max} = 624.6 nm and sulphuric acid (98% pure). An accurate quantity of dye (500 mg) was dissolved in a liter of double distilled water to prepare stock solution (500 mg/L). All chemical used were of analytical grade. Experimental solutions of desired concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilutions.

Analytical measurements :

UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202, India) was used to determine the concentration of BG in solutions. The digital pH meter (Systronics 335, Ahmedabad, India) was used to maintain appropriate pH, FTIR spectrophotometer (ABB FTLA 2000, Hyderabad, India) and scanning electron microscope (FEI Quanta 200 MK2, Japan) were used for the characterization of the adsorbent.

Batch experimental programme :

Adsorption studies were carried out by batch mode to obtain the rate and equilibrium data. The experiments were performed to observe the effect of important parameters like contact time, pH, initial dye concentration and effect of adsorbent dose on the adsorptive removal of BG, all the experiments were conducted at the temperature 303 ± 2 K. In each adsorption experiment, 25 mL of dye solution of known concentration was added to 0.1 g of OFHC in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and the mixture was stirred in thermostatic orbital shaker (Shivam, India Pvt. Ltd.) at 100 rpm. The samples were withdrawn from the shaker at the predetermined time intervals and the adsorbent were separated from the solutions using

Whatman filter paper No. 42. Residual dye concentration was determined from absorbance values measured before and after treatment with OFHC at wavelength 624.4 nm with the double beam UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Experiments were also carried out in the pH range 2–12, which was adjusted by using 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH solutions, to find out the optimum pH for the removal of BG. In order to investigate the effect of temperature on the adsorption characteristics studies were also carried out at different temperatures, 293–323 K.

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